

Duck and Otter Creek Project, Lucas County (41.67031, -83.47613)

Since construction in June 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Duck and Otter Creek Project has been slowing flow and filtering water from Duck Creek. Surface water nutrient concentration estimates suggest that the Project wetland is functioning as a sink for phosphorus and has had a small and more variable influence on reducing nitrogen concentrations; however, flow measurements are needed to validate these conclusions. A reduction in water levels since construction, either due to drought conditions over 2024 or the re-grading of the site that occurred during construction to slow flow and increase water retention, suggests that the Project has the potential to retain and treat greater volumes of water. Future measurements of water flow at the monitoring stations are needed to evaluate nutrient load reductions for the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this coastal flowthrough Project is passively managed. The Project has 10.56 acres of restored or created wetland and features several wetland pools situated along reconfigured meandering natural stream channel. Water enters from Duck Creek upstream and flows slowly through the Project before outflowing to Duck Creek downstream.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess potential for directing additional water inputs to the Project in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).
- Consider expanding the footprint of the Project by implementing additional components of the planned floodplain wetland restoration and stream channel naturalization projects along Duck and Otter Creeks.

Current monitoring data based on concentrations alone suggest that the wetland is retaining some phosphorus and relatively less nitrogen; however, flow measurements are needed to reliably assess the volume of water treated and, therefore, nutrient load. Additionally, no significant high-flow events have been sampled for the Project, and event-based storm sampling should be prioritized during subsequent monitoring to characterize the wetland's nutrient retention and loading over a larger range of hydrological regimes.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.